

22 **Keywords:** Coalbed methane, Microwave irradiation, Hydraulic fracture, Matrix-
23 fracture system, Gas desorption and migration

24 1 Introduction

25 Coalbed methane (CBM) represents a low-emission and effective resource, widely
26 recognized as a potential green alternative to conventional fossil fuels. In recent years,
27 with the growing global energy demand and increasing environmental pressure, CBM
28 has received extensive attention. Its exploration and production are significant for
29 optimizing the energy consumption structure and promoting environmental
30 sustainability¹. In particular, gas-bearing coalbeds generally have a high gas content,
31 low pressure, and poor permeability, which pose considerable challenges to efficient
32 gas extraction, especially in deep coal formations². Moreover, CBM exists primarily in
33 two forms within the reservoir: adsorbed gas and free gas³. Approximately 80% to 90%
34 of CBM exists in an adsorbed state within the micropores of the matrix. After desorption,
35 the gas diffuses from the matrix into fractures and then migrates toward the production
36 well in a free state (Fig. 1)^{4,5}.

37

38 Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of gas storage and transport

39 In conventional enhanced CBM recovery techniques, hydraulic fracturing is a
40 widely adopted method to promote desorption. Although it can effectively stimulate gas
41 desorption under certain conditions, it often causes water lock effects⁶. In addition, the
42 injection of chemical agents may result in permanent alterations to the coal pore
43 structure, further limiting the effective desorption and migration of gas⁷⁻¹⁰. To
44 overcome these issues, researchers have proposed various emerging physical
45 stimulation technologies, such as radio-frequency heating^{11,12} and laser irradiation^{13,14}.
46 Although these methods have demonstrated certain production enhancement effects
47 under laboratory conditions, they still face technical and economic challenges in
48 practical applications. Therefore, effectively improving the desorption and migration of
49 methane remains a critical issue in CBM development.

50 Microwave heating has recently gained attention as a novel and promising
51 method¹⁵. The frequency of microwaves ranges from 300 MHz to 300 GHz, can be
52 absorbed by coal to generate internal heat. This heat raises the coal temperature,
53 enhancing gas desorption and migration. Microwaves are considered a promising
54 technique for enhanced CBM recovery. Compared with traditional techniques,
55 microwave heating offers several advantages: non-contact operation, rapid and
56 selective heating, and efficient localized energy delivery¹⁶. As a result, it has found
57 applications in various fields.

58 Previous investigations have proven the feasibility and effectiveness of using
59 microwave heating for extracting unconventional natural gas¹⁷. Denney Dennis

60 reported that microwave heating can effectively mitigate water lock effects and
61 significantly improve permeability, boosting CBM production¹⁸. Fianu et al. revealed
62 through simulations that microwave heating significantly promoted gas desorption,
63 leading to a 25% increase in total output over the course of a year¹⁹. He Li et al.
64 proposed an electromagnetic-thermo-hydro-mechanical (ETHM) model. Their findings
65 confirmed that microwave heating plays a key role in increasing gas desorption, with
66 cumulative CBM production rising by 43.9%²⁰. Liu et al. investigate the multiphysics
67 coupling mechanisms during microwave-assisted shale gas recovery. The results
68 indicated that microwave injection increased the matrix temperature, caused water
69 evaporation, reduced water saturation, and enhanced gas desorption, thereby improving
70 recovery efficiency²¹. Sun et al. built a coupled ETHM model for CBM recovery based
71 on directional long-borehole drainage. Their research indicated that microwave thermal
72 injection increased cumulative production by approximately 80%²². Huang et al.
73 obtained the permeability distribution using the strain–permeability relationship. Their
74 findings confirmed the permeability-enhancing effect of microwave heating²³. Zhu et
75 al. examined the evolution of heat and methane concentration, while conducting a
76 sensitivity analysis on water content. Their study showed that microwave heating
77 enhanced porosity and permeability near the waveguide²⁴. Li et al. used μ -CT to
78 construct an equivalent pore–fracture network model and analyzed changes in the pore–
79 fracture structure under microwave irradiation. Their results indicated that microwaves
80 improve connectivity and spatial distribution, increasing permeability and promoting

81 methane production²⁵. Liu et al. developed a methane adsorption model considering
82 moisture. Their study demonstrated that microwave irradiation raised matrix
83 temperature, enhanced gas desorption, and reduced water content, significantly
84 affecting shale gas production²⁶. Xu et al. proposed a novel shale gas enhancement
85 method that promotes methane migration and reservoir modification through
86 microwave field control. The results showed that microwave heating increased shale
87 porosity and permeability and significantly reduced the maximum CH₄ adsorption
88 capacity²⁷. In summary, few have addressed how microwave heating combined with
89 hydraulic fracturing can enhance underground CBM production.

90 This paper proposes an innovative method for CBM extraction using microwave
91 yield enhancement technology. Based on theories of electromagnetism, heat transfer,
92 solid mechanics, and fluid flow, an ETHM fully coupled CBM recovery model was
93 developed and implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics to study the effects of
94 microwave irradiation on the storage and migration of CBM. Fig. 2 illustrates the
95 schematic of CBM extraction under microwave irradiation, where multiple vertical
96 wells are employed to achieve microwave-enhanced gas recovery. The following
97 outlines the structure of the paper: Section 2 derives the governing equations for the
98 multiphysics fields; Section 3 describes the coupling mechanisms between different
99 physical fields; Section 4 discusses the variation of coal seam temperature, pressure,
100 and gas content, while analyzes the effects of microwave frequency, power, and
101 hydraulic fractures on CBM extraction efficiency; finally, Section 5 presents the

102 conclusions.

103

104 Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of microwave heating stimulation of hydraulically fractured CBM
105 reservoir

106 2 Governing equations

107 Coal is a porous material with multiple phases and components, characterized by
108 diverse composition, complex structure, and significant anisotropy. Given the
109 challenges in modeling electromagnetic fields, multiphase heat transfer, and mass
110 transport, the following basic assumptions are made in this study:

- 111 1) CBM satisfies the ideal gas equation.
- 112 2) Coal is an isotropic, homogeneous elastic material.
- 113 3) The temperature of the coal in the initial state is uniform.
- 114 4) The coal's porosity, thermal conductivity, dielectric constant, and specific heat
115 capacity are isotropic.
- 116 5) No chemical reactions occur during the microwave heating process.

117 2.1 Electromagnetic wave excitation

118 The propagation of electromagnetic waves in space follows Maxwell's equations,
 119 which outline the temporal and spatial variations of electric and magnetic fields under
 120 specific field sources:

$$121 \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{J} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_{ec} \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

122 where \mathbf{E} denotes the electric field vector, while \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{H} correspond to magnetic flux
 123 density and magnetic field intensity, respectively. \mathbf{D} represents the electric displacement
 124 field, \mathbf{J} signifies the density of electric current, and ρ_{ec} stands for the electric charge per
 125 unit volume.

126 To obtain a numerical solution for the electromagnetic field, the frequency-domain
 127 approach is employed, which leads to the derivation of the Helmholtz vector equation²⁸:

$$128 \quad \nabla \times \mu_r^{-1} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) - k_0^2 \left(\epsilon_r - \frac{j\sigma}{\omega\epsilon_0} \right) \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad (2)$$

129 where μ_r stands for the relative magnetic permeability, k_0 represents the wave number
 130 in free space, σ denotes electrical conductivity, ϵ_r refers to the relative permittivity, ω
 131 denotes the angular frequency, and j is the imaginary unit. k_0 is represented as:

$$132 \quad k_0 = \frac{\omega}{c_0} \quad (3)$$

133 here, c_0 denotes the vacuum speed of light.

134 2.2 Heat transfer

135 The temperature field of coal is governed by the heat transfer equation for porous

136 media^{29,30}:

$$137 \quad \rho_c C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_c C_p \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T + K \alpha_T T \frac{\partial \varepsilon_v}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = Q_{mw} \quad (4)$$

138 where ρ_c represents the density of the coal, and C_p refers to its specific heat capacity
139 under constant stress conditions, the parameter K stands for the bulk modulus that
140 characterizes the compressibility of coal, \mathbf{u} denotes the velocity field, while \mathbf{q} describes
141 the conductive heat flux within the medium, the coefficient α_T governs thermal
142 expansion, and T denotes the coal temperature, the term ε_v denotes the volumetric strain
143 of the coal, whereas Q_{mw} incorporates additional heat sources.

144 The conductive heat flux \mathbf{q} is represented by:

$$145 \quad \mathbf{q} = -k \nabla T \quad (5)$$

146 here, k denotes the thermal conductivity.

147 The thermal source is provided by microwave irradiation through electromagnetic
148 losses, and is mathematically represented by the term Q_{mw} :

$$149 \quad Q_{mw} = \frac{1}{2} \text{Re}(\mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{E}^*) + \frac{1}{2} \text{Re}(i\omega \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{H}^*) \quad (6)$$

150 2.3 Coal deformation

151 In consideration of gas pressure, thermal expansion, gas sorption, and other
152 pertinent factors, the non-isothermal solid deformation equation of coal is defined as³⁰⁻
153 ³³:

$$154 \quad \Delta \varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2G} \Delta \sigma_{ij} - \left(\frac{1}{6G} - \frac{1}{9K} \right) \Delta \sigma_{kk} \delta_{ij} + \frac{\alpha}{3K} \Delta p_m \delta_{ij} + \frac{\beta}{3K} \Delta p_f \delta_{ij} + \frac{\alpha_T}{3} \Delta T \delta_{ij} + \frac{\Delta \varepsilon_s}{3} \delta_{ij} \quad (7)$$

155 where ε_{ij} and σ_{ij} represent the total strain and stress tensors, respectively.

156 $\sigma_{kk} = \sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}$ denotes the sum of normal stresses, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, the
157 shear modulus G and bulk modulus K of coal are defined as $G = E / [2(1+\nu)]$ and

158 $K = E / [3(1 - 2\nu)]$, where E is Young's modulus and ν is Poisson's ratio. K_s denotes the
159 bulk modulus of the coal skeleton, and K_n represents the individual bulk modulus of
160 natural fractures. $\alpha = 1 - K / K_s$ and $\beta = 1 - K / aK_n$ are the Biot's coefficients of
161 matrix and natural fracture, respectively. gas pressures within the matrix and fracture
162 domains are represented by p_m and p_f , and ε_s indicates the volumetric strain induced by
163 gas adsorption.

164 According to Eq.(7), the volumetric strain variation in the coal medium can be
165 derived in the following form:

$$166 \quad \Delta\varepsilon_v = -\frac{1}{K}(\Delta\bar{\sigma} - \alpha\Delta p_m - \beta\Delta p_f) + \alpha_T\Delta T + \Delta\varepsilon_s \quad (8)$$

167 where $\varepsilon_v = \varepsilon_{11} + \varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33}$, and $\bar{\sigma} = -\sigma_{kk} / 3$.

168 The volumetric strain ε_s due to methane adsorption in the matrix is described
169 as²⁰:

$$170 \quad \varepsilon_s = \alpha_s V_s \quad (9)$$

171 where α_s is the sorption strain coefficient, and V_s refers to the adsorbed gas content
172 within the matrix.

173 V_s can be quantified with the following modified Langmuir equation^{34,35}:

$$174 \quad V_s = \frac{V_L p_m}{p_m + p_L} \exp\left[-\frac{c_2}{1 + c_1 p_m}(T - T_r)\right] \quad (10)$$

175 where T_r is the reference temperature for the gas sorption tests, V_L and p_L represent the
176 Langmuir volume and pressure, respectively. c_1 and c_2 are empirical coefficients
177 reflecting pressure and temperature, respectively.

178 Inserting Eq. (10) into Eq. (9) yields:

179
$$\varepsilon_s = \frac{\alpha_s V_L p_m}{p_m + p_L} \exp \left[-\frac{c_2 (T - T_r)}{1 + c_1 p_m} \right] \quad (11)$$

180 Considering the force balance and coupling of strain-displacement relations, the
 181 expression is obtained^{36,37}:

182
$$\sigma_{ij,j} + f_i = 0 \quad (12)$$

183
$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) \quad (13)$$

184 where f_i represents the net body force along direction i , and u_i ($i=x, y, z$) is the
 185 displacement component in the corresponding direction.

186 By incorporating Eqs.(7) and (13) into Eq.(12), the updated coal deformation
 187 model becomes:

188
$$G u_{i,jj} + \frac{G}{1-2\nu} u_{j,ji} - \alpha p_{m,i} - \beta p_{f,i} - K \alpha_T T_{,i} - K \varepsilon_{s,i} + f_i = 0 \quad (14)$$

189 2.4 Gas flow in coal matrix

190 The governing equation for methane transport within the coal matrix is formulated
 191 as follows^{20,22,26}:

192
$$\frac{\partial m_m}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{gm} \mathbf{u}_m) = -Q_m \quad (15)$$

193 where $\mathbf{u}_m = -\frac{k_m}{\mu} \nabla p_m$, \mathbf{u}_m and k_m denote the Darcy velocity and the permeability of the
 194 matrix, respectively, μ is the dynamic viscosity of methane, m_m refers to the total
 195 methane mass retained in the matrix, ρ_{gm} is the gas density inside the matrix, and Q_m
 196 represents a mass source term.

197 m_m consists of both free-phase and adsorbed methane within the matrix³⁸:

198
$$m_m = \rho_{gm} \phi_m + \rho_{gs} \rho_c V_s \quad (16)$$

199 where ϕ_m stands for the matrix porosity, while ρ_{gs} is the standard methane density.

200 For methane transport within porous medium i ($i=m, f, F$), the relationship is
 201 described by the ideal gas law:

$$202 \quad \rho_{gi} = \frac{M_g p_i}{RT} \quad (17)$$

203 ϕ_m can be written as a function of the effective strain^{20,39}:

$$204 \quad \phi_m = \phi_{m0} + \alpha \Delta \varepsilon_e = \phi_{m0} + \alpha \left(\Delta \varepsilon_v + \frac{\Delta p_m}{K_s} - \Delta \varepsilon_s - \alpha_T \Delta T \right) \quad (18)$$

205 where ϕ_{m0} denotes the initial porosity of the matrix, $\Delta \varepsilon_e$ represents the total effective
 206 volumetric strain, consisting of four contributions: total volumetric strain, $\Delta \varepsilon_v$, coal
 207 matrix compressive strain, $\Delta p_m / K_s$, adsorption-induced volumetric strain, $\Delta \varepsilon_s$, and
 208 thermal-induced strain, $\alpha_T \Delta T$.

209 Permeability and porosity satisfy the cubic law:

$$210 \quad \frac{k_m}{k_{m0}} = \left(\frac{\phi_m}{\phi_{m0}} \right)^3 \quad (19)$$

211 where k_{m0} represents the initial permeability of the matrix.

212 The matrix permeability changes with variations in porosity. By inserting Eq.(18)
 213 into Eq.(19), we obtain:

$$214 \quad k_m = k_{m0} \left[1 + \frac{\alpha}{\phi_{m0}} \left(\Delta \varepsilon_v + \frac{\Delta p_m}{K_s} - \Delta \varepsilon_s - \alpha_T \Delta T \right) \right]^3 \quad (20)$$

215 Combining Eqs.(15)~(20), the final expression governing gas flow in the matrix
 216 is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\frac{1}{T} \left[\phi_m + \frac{\alpha p_m}{K_s} \right] + \left[\frac{R \rho_{gs} \rho_c V_L}{M_g} - \frac{\alpha p_m \alpha_s V_L}{T} \right] \right] \\
& \left[\frac{p_L}{(p_m + p_L)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2}{1 + c_1 p} (T - T_r)\right) + \frac{p_L}{(p_m + p_L)} \right] \left\{ \frac{\partial p_m}{\partial t} - \right. \\
& \left. \exp\left(-\frac{c_2}{1 + c_1 p_m} (T - T_r)\right) \frac{c_1 c_2}{(1 + c_1 p_m)^2} (T - T_r) \right\} \\
217 \quad & \left[\frac{\phi p_m}{T^2} + \frac{p_m \alpha \alpha_T}{T} \right] + \left[\frac{R \rho_{gs} \rho_c V_L}{M_g} - \frac{\alpha p_m \alpha_s V_L}{T} \right] \left\{ \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \frac{p_m \alpha}{T} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_v}{\partial t} + \right. \\
& \left. \frac{p_L}{(p_m + p_L)} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2}{1 + c_1 p_m} (T - T_r)\right) \frac{c_2}{(1 + c_1 p_m)} \right\} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \frac{p_m \alpha}{T} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_v}{\partial t} + \quad (21) \\
& \nabla \cdot \left(-\frac{k_m}{\mu} \frac{p_m}{T} \nabla \cdot p_m \right) = -\frac{R}{M_g} \omega (p_m - p_f)
\end{aligned}$$

218 where ω denotes the gas exchange coefficient between the matrix and the natural
219 fracture, defined by ^{40,41}:

$$220 \quad \omega = 8 \left(1 + \frac{2}{a^2} \right) \frac{k_m}{\mu} \quad (22)$$

221 where a represents the shape factor associated with the matrix geometry.

222 2.5 Gas flow in natural fracture

223 According to the mass conservation principle, methane migration through natural
224 fractures is expressed as follows^{30,42}:

$$225 \quad \frac{\partial(\rho_{gf} \phi_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{gf} \mathbf{u}_f) = Q_m \quad (23)$$

226 where $\mathbf{u}_f = -\frac{k_f}{\mu} \nabla p_f$, \mathbf{u}_f and k_f denote the Darcy velocity and the permeability of the

227 natural fracture, and ϕ_f is the porosity of the natural fracture.

228 ϕ_f is formulated as a function of the effective volumetric strain⁴³:

$$229 \quad \phi_f = \phi_{f0} + 3\beta(1 - R_m) \left(\Delta \varepsilon_v + \frac{\Delta p_f}{K_s} - \Delta \varepsilon_s - \alpha_T \Delta T \right) \quad (24)$$

230 where ϕ_{f0} stands for the initial porosity of natural fracture, $R_m = E / E_s$ represents the
 231 Young's modulus ratio between the coal bulk and the matrix.

232 Permeability and porosity satisfy the cubic law:

$$233 \quad \frac{k_f}{k_{f0}} = \left(\frac{\phi_f}{\phi_{f0}} \right)^3 \quad (25)$$

234 where k_{f0} is the initial permeability of the natural fracture.

235 By inserting Eq.(24) into Eq.(25), the updated fracture permeability can be
 236 expressed as:

$$237 \quad k_f = k_{f0} \left[1 + \frac{3\beta(1-R_m)}{\phi_{f0}} (\Delta\varepsilon_v + \frac{\Delta p_f}{K_s} - \Delta\varepsilon_s - \alpha_T \Delta T) \right]^3 \quad (26)$$

238 By combining Eqs.(23)~(26), the gas flow equations for the natural fracture are
 239 established:

$$240 \quad \left(\frac{\phi_f}{T} + 3\beta(1-R_m) \frac{p_f}{T} \frac{1}{K_s} \right) \frac{\partial p_f}{\partial t} - \left(\frac{\phi_f p_f}{T^2} + 3\beta(1-R_m) \frac{p_f}{T} \alpha_T \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + 3\beta(1-R_m) \frac{p_f}{T} \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon_v}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \varepsilon_s}{\partial t} \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(-\frac{k_f p_f}{\mu T} \nabla \cdot p_f \right) = \frac{R}{M_g} \omega (p_m - p_f) \quad (27)$$

241 2.6 Gas flow in hydraulic fracture

242 The transport of methane in hydraulic fractures follows the conservation law and
 243 is governed by the following equation^{30,43}:

$$244 \quad b_F \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\phi_F \rho_{gF}) + \nabla_T \cdot (-b_F \rho_{gF} \mathbf{u}_F) = 0 \quad (28)$$

245 where b_F and ϕ_F are the width and the porosity of the hydraulic fracture, and ρ_{gF}
 246 represents the gas density within the fracture. The Darcy velocity \mathbf{u}_F in the hydraulic
 247 fracture is described as:

$$248 \quad \mathbf{u}_F = -\frac{k_F}{\mu} \nabla_T p_F \quad (29)$$

249 where k_F denotes hydraulic fracture permeability, ∇_T indicates the directional gradient
 250 along the fracture, and p_F corresponds to the hydraulic fracture pressure.

251 Continuity of gas pressure and mass flux is enforced between the natural and
 252 hydraulic fractures, with the hydraulic fracture acting as an outlet boundary for the
 253 natural fracture⁴⁴:

$$254 \quad p_F = p_f \quad (30)$$

$$255 \quad \vec{u}_F = \vec{u}_f \quad (31)$$

256 where \vec{u}_F and \vec{u}_f represent the gas mass fluxes in the hydraulic and natural fractures,
 257 respectively.

258 According to the hydraulic fracture definition of the compression ratio, C_F :

$$259 \quad C_F = \frac{1}{\phi_F} \frac{d\phi_F}{dp_F} \quad (32)$$

260 Integrating Eq.(32) yields the porosity equation:

$$261 \quad \phi_F = \phi_{F0} \exp[C_F(p_F - p_{F0})] \quad (33)$$

262 where ϕ_{F0} denotes the initial porosity of the hydraulic fracture.

263 The width of the hydraulic fracture b_F is expressed as⁴³:

$$264 \quad b_F = b_{F0} \exp[C_F(p_F - p_{F0})] \quad (34)$$

265 where b_{F0} and p_{F0} correspond to the initial hydraulic fracture width and pressure,
 266 respectively.

267 k_F is described by the following relationship:

$$268 \quad k_F = k_{F0} \left(\frac{b_F}{b_{F0}} \right)^2 = k_{F0} \exp[2C_F(p_F - p_{F0})] \quad (35)$$

269 **3 Numerical implementation and model validation**

270 **3.1 Cross-coupling relationship**

271 Eqs.(2), (4) (14), (21), (27) and (28) collectively constitute the ETHM multi-
272 physics coupling mathematical model for CBM production via thermal injection. This
273 model comprises four primary physical fields: electromagnetic, thermal transfer,
274 mechanical deformation, and gas migration. The interactions among these fields are
275 illustrated in Fig. 3.

276 The electromagnetic field induces thermal injection through electromagnetic
277 energy dissipation, leading to heat accumulation within the coal seam. As shown in
278 Eqs.(18) and (20), variations in porosity and permeability respond to changes in
279 effective volumetric strain. Temperature variation induces thermal strain, leading to the
280 expansion or contraction of the coal reservoir, which consequently alters its porosity
281 and permeability. Additionally, as temperature increases, the free gas content rises,
282 resulting in pressure variations within the coal seam. Gas accumulated in high-
283 temperature zones carries part of the thermal energy and migrates toward low-pressure
284 regions, further contributing to volumetric strain. These analyses reveal that the gas
285 flow field, temperature field, and solid deformation field are bidirectionally coupled.
286 The nonlinear system of equations associated with the multi-physics fields is solved
287 using the COMSOL Multiphysics software platform.

288

289

Fig. 3 Cross-coupling relationship within the ETHM model

290 3.2 Model validation

291 To validate the proposed multi-physics coupling mathematical model, numerical

292 simulation results are assessed against field test data to ensure the model's reliability

293 and rationality. Based on the research data reported by the American EL PASO

294 Exploration & Production company and Mora et al.⁴⁵, a representative physical model

295 for CBM extraction is established. Fig. 4 illustrates a square physical domain of 568 m

296 × 568 m, where the production well is situated at the center of the model. The

297 waveguides are situated on either side of the working face, operating at a frequency of

298 0.915 GHz and a power level of 1000 W. The boundary conditions, initial conditions,

299 and simulation parameters are primarily based on the literature by Mora, Wang, and

300 others^{45–47}. The parameters employed in the validation model are provided in Table I.

301
302
303

Fig. 4 Simulation model for verification purposes
Table I Parameters used in the validation model⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷

Parameters	Variable	Value	Unit
Coal reservoir thickness	H	3.8	m
Initial gas pressure	p_0	4.82	MPa
Initial porosity	ϕ_0	0.015	1
Initial permeability	k_0	5	mD
Density of coal	ρ_c	1520	kg/m ³
Langmuir volume	V_L	0.048	m ³ /kg
Langmuir pressure	P_L	1.93	MPa
Young's modulus of coal	E	1119	MPa
Dynamic viscosity of methane	μ	1.1×10^{-6}	Pa·s

304 Fig. 5 illustrates the comparative analysis of CBM production simulation results
305 versus actual field measurements. Specifically, the scattered points represent measured
306 CBM production data, while the red and black curves correspond to the simulation
307 results under microwave-assisted and conventional conditions, respectively. As shown,
308 the simulated production rate exhibits a strong agreement with the field observations,
309 effectively capturing the overall production trend. Therefore, the developed multi-

310 physics coupled model demonstrates high reliability and applicability in characterizing
311 CBM production processes. Furthermore, the production rate under microwave-assisted
312 conditions is significantly higher than that under conventional extraction. This suggests
313 that microwave heating can elevate the coal matrix temperature, thereby enhancing the
314 desorption and migration capacity of reservoir gas. Consequently, microwave-assisted
315 extraction significantly improves CBM production efficiency, which further verifies the
316 feasibility and effectiveness of this enhanced recovery technique.

317
318 Fig. 5 Comparison between simulated and field gas production rate data

319 4 Numerical simulations and susceptibility analyses

320 4.1 Computational model and schemes

321 A two-dimensional geometric model of gas migration in a microwave-heated coal
322 reservoir was developed using the COMSOL simulation platform. The model geometry
323 is illustrated in Fig. 6. Four waveguide ports are placed symmetrically on both sides of
324 the rectangular coal reservoir. The electromagnetic wave propagates in the transverse
325 electric (TE) mode, and the microwave frequency is fixed at 915 MHz. A gas extraction

326 well is positioned at the center of the rectangular domain, where the gas pressure is
 327 maintained at 0.1 MPa. Free methane continuously migrates toward the borehole. In
 328 addition, the local mesh around the waveguide port was refined, with a cell size of
 329 0.01 m. According to the mesh sensitivity analysis, this size has been validated as
 330 suitable for the specified microwave frequency ($f = 0.915$ GHz). The model's initial and
 331 boundary conditions are presented in Table II, while the simulation parameters are
 332 detailed in Table III.

333 Fig. 6 Mesh and boundary conditions of the computational model
 334
 335

336 Table II Initial and boundary conditions

Condition	Electromagnetic	Thermal transfer	mechanical deformation	gas migration
Initial values	$E = 0$	$T = T_0$	$\mathbf{u} = 0$	$p = p_0$
Coalbed boundary	$\mathbf{n} \times (\nabla \times (\mathbf{E})) - jk\mathbf{n} \times (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{n}) = 0$	$-\mathbf{n}q = 0$	$\mathbf{n}u = 0$	$-\mathbf{n} \rho u = 0$
Waveguide Port boundary	$S = \frac{\int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{E}_1) \cdot \mathbf{E}_1}{\int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{E}_1 \cdot \mathbf{E}_1}$	$-\mathbf{n}q = 0$	$\mathbf{n}u = 0$	$-\mathbf{n} \rho u = 0$
Borehole boundary	$\mathbf{n} \times (\nabla \times (\mathbf{E})) - jk\mathbf{n} \times (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{n}) = 0$	$-\mathbf{n}q = 0$	Free	$p = p_s$

337

338

Table III Numerical simulation parameters^{20,22}

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Electromagnetic frequency	f	0.915	GHz
Electromagnetic power	P	80	W
Dielectric constant	ε'	2	-
Loss factor	ε''	0.2	-

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Electrical conductivity	σ	0.02	S/m
Density of coal	ρ_c	1250	kg/m ³
Density of methane at standard conditions	ρ_{gs}	0.717	kg/m ³
Initial temperature of coal	T_0	300	K
Thermal conductivity of coal	k	0.478	W/(m·K)
Thermal expansion coefficient	α_T	2.4×10^{-5}	K ⁻¹
Heat capacity at constant stress	C_p	1000	J/(kg·K)
Young's modulus of coal	E	2713	MPa
Young's modulus of coal grains	E_s	7979	MPa
Poisson's ratio of coal	ν	0.339	1
Coefficient for sorption-induced volumetric strain	α_s	0.06	kg/m ³
Initial gas pressure of the coal matrix	p_{m0}	2	MPa
Initial gas pressure of the natural fracture	p_{f0}	2	MPa
Dynamic viscosity of methane	μ	1.84×10^{-5}	Pa·s
Reference temperature for gas desorption tests	T_r	300	K
Langmuir volume	V_L	0.043	m ³ /kg
Langmuir pressure	P_L	1.57	MPa
Pressure coefficient	c_1	0.07	MPa ⁻¹
Temperature coefficient	c_2	0.02	K ⁻¹
Pressure at standard conditions	P_s	0.101325	MPa
Temperature at standard conditions	T_s	273	K
Initial porosity of coal matrix	ϕ_{m0}	0.01	1
Initial permeability of coal matrix	k_{m0}	1×10^{-19}	m ²
Initial porosity of natural fracture	ϕ_{f0}	0.03	1
Initial permeability of natural fracture	k_{f0}	1×10^{-15}	m ²
Initial porosity of hydraulic fracture	ϕ_{F0}	0.1	1
Compressibility of hydraulic fracture	C_F	1×10^{-9}	1/Pa
Initial width of hydraulic fracture	b_{F0}	1.1×10^{-4}	m

339

340 4.2 Simulation results analyses

341 4.2.1 Evolution of temperature

342 The coal seam, based on its dielectric properties, absorbs electromagnetic energy

343 and transforms it into heat. The resulting temperature variation significantly influences

344 both the gas migration behavior and the mechanical response of the coal reservoir.

345 Therefore, the temperature field serves as a critical factor in the coal seam's response
346 under microwave heating. In high-temperature regions, heat transfer is primarily
347 governed by thermal conduction and convection, with gas flow processes occurring
348 simultaneously with heat transport. Moreover, the magnitude of the temperature
349 gradient directly affects the rate of thermal conduction.

350 Fig. 7 exhibits three-dimensional visualizations of the thermal evolution in coal
351 seams under microwave irradiation. Before heating, the entire coal seam remains at 300
352 K. As the heating duration extends, the temperature near the waveguide ports rises
353 gradually, and the high-temperature zone progressively penetrates further into the coal
354 seam. Simultaneously, the gas migration direction is oriented toward the borehole.
355 Under the joint influence of heat conduction in the matrix and thermal convection of
356 gas, the heat generated by the waveguide is continuously transferred toward lower-
357 temperature regions. As illustrated in Fig. 8, the temperature increases steadily over
358 time, with thermal conductivity of the reservoir playing a significant role in this process.
359 By day 360, the temperature around the borehole has increased to 310K, indicating that,
360 under the current thermal conductivity, heat accumulation occurs within the coal seam,
361 leading to a general temperature rise across various regions. A cross-sectional centerline
362 through the reservoir [indicated by the red line in Fig. 6] is selected for analysis, and the
363 corresponding temperature distribution along this line is shown in Fig. 9. The
364 temperature along the monitoring line exhibits a U-shaped distribution, and a longer

365 microwave irradiation period leads to a larger temperature gradient.

366

367

Fig. 7 Thermal evolution of the coalbed during microwave irradiation

368

369

Fig. 8 Temperature evolution at points A, B, C, and D

370

371

Fig. 9 Temperature variation along the monitoring line during 360 days of CBM production

372 4.2.2 Evolution of gas pressure

373

Fig. 10 (a) illustrates the pressure distribution in the coal matrix following 360

374

days of thermal recovery under microwave irradiation. High-pressure zones are

375

primarily concentrated in the central region of the reservoir. This phenomenon is

376

attributed to the substantial desorption of adsorbed gas near the waveguide, which then

377

migrates through the fracture network toward the production well. Influenced by both

378

temperature and pressure gradients, gas continuously flows toward the extraction

379

borehole, resulting in a pronounced pressure differential. Fig. 10 (b) presents the

380

pressure distribution in the natural fracture after 360 days. Due to microwave irradiation,

381

gas pressure is generally higher near the waveguide, while significantly reduced near

382

the production well and hydraulic fractures, forming a distinct pressure funnel. The

383

evolution of matrix pressure along the monitoring line at varying extraction times is

384

illustrated in Fig. 10 (c). Following a 30-day production, a significant pressure buildup

385

up to 2.9 MPa is observed near the waveguide, while a sharp pressure decline is detected

386 around hydraulic fractures and the extraction well. This is mainly due to the limited
 387 initial temperature distribution during early-stage microwave heating, resulting in a
 388 relatively low desorption rate. As extraction proceeds to 360 days, the intensified gas
 389 desorption and diffusion result in a gradual reduction in matrix pressure near the
 390 waveguides, along with a reduction in the pressure peak. Fig. 10 (d) shows the pressure
 391 variation in natural fractures over time. By day 30, evident gas migration pathways have
 392 formed. The presence of hydraulic fractures accelerates localized pressure dissipation.
 393 With ongoing extraction, the pressure within the natural fractures exhibits a continuous
 394 decrease. Microwave heating significantly enhances gas desorption, while hydraulic
 395 fractures further facilitate gas migration toward the production well, thereby improving
 396 overall extraction efficiency.

397

398

399 Fig. 10 Gas pressure distribution in the coal reservoir: (a) Pressure contour of the matrix at 360

400 days; (b) Pressure contour of the natural fractures at 360 days; (c) Pressure in the matrix along the
401 monitoring line; (d) Pressure in natural fractures along the monitoring line.

402 **4.2.3 Evolution of gas content**

403 The total quantity of CBM is the sum of the adsorbed and free state gases. The
404 expression is given as follows⁴⁸:

$$405 \quad V_{total} = \frac{V_L p_m}{p_m + p_L} \exp \left[-\frac{c_2}{1 + c_1 p_m} (T - T_r) \right] + \frac{\phi p_m T_s}{p_s T \rho_c} \quad (36)$$

406 where V_{total} denotes the total amount of gas, with T_s and p_s representing the standard
407 temperature and pressure, respectively.

408 The transformation between adsorbed and free gas is affected by both temperature
409 and gas pressure. Elevated temperature and reduced gas pressure facilitate the transition
410 of methane from the adsorbed phase to the free phase. This section investigates the
411 evolution of gas content under non-isothermal conditions to analyze the gas migration
412 mechanism at different stages of microwave heating. Fig. 11 illustrates the evolution of
413 total gas content during microwave-assisted extraction, with an initial value of 24.2 m³/t.
414 Under microwave heating, significant gas content reduction occurs not only near the
415 borehole and hydraulic fractures but also in regions where the coal temperature rises.
416 Thermal desorption contributes to this decline, with greater reductions observed in
417 higher-temperature zones. As microwave heating progresses, the gas content of CBM
418 continuously declines, and the gradient of gas content becomes less pronounced. By
419 day 360, the gas content drops to 0.075~9.44 m³/t throughout the reservoir.

420

421

Fig. 11 Total gas content evolution during microwave irradiation

422

Fig. 12 illustrates the variation of adsorbed and free gas under microwave-assisted

423

extraction. Adsorbed gas constitutes the predominant share in terms of total gas storage.

424

Moreover, as the distance from the borehole grows, its content initially increases rapidly

425

and then gradually decreases. A notable reduction in adsorbed gas is observed near the

426

microwave sources, indicating the advantage of microwave-assisted CBM recovery, as

427

the irradiation promotes desorption and facilitates gas extraction.

428

429

Fig. 12 Temporal evolution of gas content during microwave-assisted CBM extraction: (a)

430

Adsorbed gas; (b) Free gas

431

4.3 Susceptibility analyses

432 **4.3.1 Effect of microwave frequency**

433 To investigate the influence of microwave frequency on CBM desorption and
434 migration, this section examines reservoir responses under four microwave frequencies:
435 0 MHz (conventional extraction), 915 MHz, 2450 MHz, and 5800 MHz. The
436 microwave irradiation characteristics significantly influence the coal matrix's ability to
437 absorb electromagnetic waves and convert energy. The dielectric properties of coal
438 significantly affect its internal temperature distribution, and these properties vary with
439 water content and temperature under different microwave frequencies.

440 Fig. 13(a) presents the cumulative gas production curves under various microwave
441 frequencies. After 360 days of extraction, the cumulative gas production under 0 MHz,
442 915 MHz, 2450 MHz, and 5800 MHz was 2630 m³, 2857 m³, 2691 m³, and 2684 m³,
443 respectively. The corresponding production increases were 8.6%, 2.1%, and 2.3%,
444 indicating that microwave heating at 915 MHz significantly enhances CBM output,
445 while extraction efficiency remains low at medium and high frequencies. Fig. 13 (b)
446 demonstrates the effect of frequency on gas production rate. In the early extraction stage,
447 the 915 MHz frequency consistently yields higher daily gas output than other
448 frequencies and the conventional case. However, after 180 days, the daily production
449 under 915 MHz slightly decreases, likely due to the early-stage release of easily
450 desorbed methane, resulting in a reduced gas content in the matrix. These results
451 suggest that low-frequency microwave irradiation is more effective in promoting
452 methane desorption and release. Fig. 13 (c) represents the temperature distribution

453 along the monitoring line corresponding to various microwave frequencies. The
 454 temperature near the microwave port reached 491 K, 415 K, and 336 K under 915 MHz,
 455 2450 MHz, and 5800 MHz, respectively, while the temperatures near the extraction
 456 well were 310 K, 304 K, and 301 K, respectively. These results indicate that 915 MHz
 457 delivers more effective heating compared to higher frequencies, demonstrating that
 458 low-frequency microwave irradiation is more beneficial in enhancing the thermal effect.
 459 Fig. 13 (d) displays the evolution of adsorbed methane along the monitoring line at 360
 460 days. Under conventional extraction (0 MHz), desorption is primarily influenced by the
 461 pressure gradient, and the adsorbed gas remains at a high level. In contrast, at 915 MHz,
 462 the adsorbed gas content near the microwave port is nearly depleted. The methane
 463 adsorption levels under 2450 MHz and 5800 MHz remain relatively high, indicating
 464 that low-frequency microwaves result in more effective heating, enhanced desorption,
 465 and faster methane migration.

466

467

468 Fig. 13 Evolution of gas production and reservoir characteristics: (a) Cumulative gas production;
 469 (b) Gas production rate; (c) Temperature distribution along the monitoring line at 360 days; (d)
 470 Adsorbed gas distribution along the monitoring line at 360 days

471 4.3.2 Effect of microwave power

472 Fig. 14(a) illustrates the cumulative CBM production curves under various
 473 microwave powers. An increase in microwave power leads to a notable enhancement
 474 in cumulative gas production. Through 360 days of continuous extraction, the
 475 cumulative output under microwave powers of 0 W, 40 W, 80 W, 140 W, and 200 W
 476 reached 2630 m³, 2689 m³, 2999 m³, 3061 m³, and 3089 m³, respectively. Compared
 477 with conventional extraction (0 W), production increases of 2%, 14%, 16%, and 17%.
 478 The findings demonstrate that microwave irradiation significantly enhances CBM
 479 recovery. Fig. 14(b) illustrates the daily gas production rates under various microwave
 480 power levels. As the power increases, the initial gas production rate rises significantly.
 481 Under conventional extraction (0 W), the methane production rate is the lowest.
 482 However, after 180 days of microwave application, differences in production rates
 483 among the power levels become less pronounced. From Fig. 14(c), we can find that the
 484 permeability remains almost stable under conventional conditions. However, under
 485 microwave irradiation, the permeability at point C initially increases marginally and

486 then decreases significantly. This is mainly attributed to matrix expansion caused by
487 the temperature increase at point C, which leads to a reduction in permeability.
488 Furthermore, higher microwave power levels lead to a more pronounced reduction in
489 permeability. Therefore, selecting an appropriate microwave power level is critical for
490 practical engineering applications. Based on the simulation results, a power level of 80
491 W offers a favorable energy efficiency ratio.

492 As depicted in Fig. 14(d), the temperature at monitoring point C reaches 306 K
493 under 40 W microwave power and rises to 358 K under 200 W, marking a 17% increase.
494 This highlights the significant influence of microwave power on reservoir heating
495 performance. Fig. 14(e) presents the matrix gas pressure profiles along the monitoring
496 line under different microwave powers. It can be observed that the pressure near the
497 microwave port is inversely proportional to the microwave power, indirectly
498 confirming the role of microwave irradiation in enhancing methane desorption and
499 transport. In addition, the peak pressure increases with rising microwave power. Fig.
500 14(f) presents the pressure distribution curve along the monitoring line for natural
501 fractures. The pressure profiles exhibit a funnel-shaped distribution, with gas pressure
502 decreasing from both microwave ports toward the borehole. Methane molecules in the
503 natural fractures can be transported either through hydraulic fractures to the production
504 well or be directly extracted by the production well. In contrast, gas stored in the matrix
505 must initially diffuse into the natural fracture system prior to extraction, resulting in
506 significantly different pressure distributions between the matrix and the fracture

507 systems. In practical applications, it is essential to select an appropriate microwave
 508 power level to avoid adverse effects on CBM recovery caused by excessive
 509 temperature-induced permeability reduction.

513 Fig. 14 Effects of microwave power on production behavior and reservoir characteristics: (a) Gas
 514 production; (b) Gas production rate; (c) Permeability ratio at monitoring point C; (d) Temperature
 515 distribution along the monitoring line at 360 days; (e) Gas pressure of the matrix along the
 516 monitoring line at 360 days; (f) Gas pressure of the natural fractures along the monitoring line at
 517 360 days

518 **4.3.3 Effect of hydraulic fracture**

519 During the microwave-assisted CBM extraction process, four scenarios with
520 hydraulic fracture lengths of 0 m (no fracture), 5 m, 10 m, and 15 m were designed to
521 analyze the evolution characteristics of reservoir parameters under different fracture
522 scales. Fig. 15 (a) shows the cumulative production curves for various fracture lengths.
523 Compared with the case without fractures, the cumulative production increased by 5.3%,
524 6.7%, and 7.0% for fracture lengths of 5 m, 10 m, and 15 m, respectively, indicating
525 that appropriately extending the hydraulic fracture length can effectively enhance CBM
526 production. Fig. 15 (b) presents the variations in production rate under different fracture
527 lengths. Hydraulic fractures provide additional pathways for gas migration, and longer
528 fractures result in higher initial production rates. The production curves for $L = 10$ m
529 and $L = 15$ m are nearly identical, suggesting that beyond a certain threshold, the
530 enhancement effect of fracture extension on CBM recovery tends to saturate.

531 Fig. 15 (c) shows the matrix pressure distribution curves under different fracture
532 lengths. The peak pressure in the central high-pressure zone of the coal reservoir
533 decreases with increasing fracture length. As the fracture length extends from 10 m to
534 15 m, the matrix pressure shows little variation, indicating a threshold effect of fracture
535 length on matrix pressure. Fig. 15 (d) presents the pressure distribution in the natural
536 fractures under various fracture lengths. Gas pressure within natural fractures declines
537 progressively from both sides toward the production well, with a sharp pressure drop
538 near the hydraulic fractures. From Fig. 16, the overall pressure in natural fractures
539 decreases with increasing fracture length, and the pressure drop becomes more rapid as

540 the fracture length increases. The extension of fracture length significantly enhances
 541 gas transport, enabling effective desorption and migration of gas from distant areas of
 542 the reservoir to the production well, thereby markedly improving the overall production
 543 efficiency.
 544

545

546

547

548

549

Fig. 15 Effects of hydraulic fracture length: (a) Gas production; (b) Gas production rate; (c) Gas pressure of the matrix along the monitoring line at 360 days; (d) Gas pressure of the natural fractures along the monitoring line at 360 days

550

551

Fig. 16 Pressure distribution in natural fractures under different hydraulic fracture lengths

552

4.4 Optimization of microwave power and hydraulic fracture layout

553

In this section, a series of combination schemes was developed to examine the

554

coupled effects of hydraulic fracture length and microwave power on CBM recovery

555

efficiency. The fracture lengths were set to 0 m, 5 m, 10 m, and 15 m, and microwave

556

power levels included 0 W, 40 W, 80 W, 140 W, and 200 W.

557

As shown in Fig. 17 and Fig. 18, under conventional extraction conditions,

558

increasing the fracture length from 0 m to 15 m enhances cumulative gas production by

559

approximately 17.5%, suggesting that fracture extension can enhance gas release and

560

transport to some extent. Under the same microwave power condition, increasing

561

fracture length generally leads to higher cumulative production. This is primarily

562

because longer fractures provide more efficient gas migration channels, promoting

563

faster desorption of adsorbed gas and its transport to the production well, thereby

564

increasing output. However, as the microwave power reaches 200 W, the production

565

improvement from increasing the fracture length from 0 m to 15 m is only 2.9%. This

566

suggests that at elevated temperatures, enhanced thermal expansion of the matrix may

567

damage the integrity of existing natural and hydraulic fractures, reducing their

568 conductivity and limiting the effective migration of desorbed gas.

569

570

Fig. 17 Heat map of output with different layouts

571

572

Fig. 18 Cumulative output map of different layouts

573

Fig. 19 illustrates the pressure distribution in natural fractures after 360 days under

574

different layouts. The gas pressure in natural fractures is jointly influenced by both

575

fracture length and microwave power, displaying significant variation. When $L = 0$ m,

576

the pressure in natural fractures increases with higher microwave power. However, once

577

hydraulic fractures are introduced, the pressure in natural fractures decreases with

578 increasing microwave power, indicating that microwave heating facilitates CBM
 579 desorption and migration. Longer hydraulic fractures are associated with lower gas
 580 pressures and larger pressure drops, confirming that under microwave heating,
 581 extended fractures significantly improve gas transport pathways and facilitate the
 582 transport of desorbed gas toward the borehole. Nevertheless, at elevated microwave
 583 power levels, the effect of fracture length on gas pressure becomes less pronounced,
 584 possibly due to deformation of the fracture structure induced by thermal expansion of
 585 the matrix. Therefore, in microwave-assisted CBM extraction, it is crucial to optimize
 586 the match between hydraulic fracture scale and microwave power to achieve higher
 587 extraction efficiency.

588
 589

Fig. 19 Pressure distribution of natural fractures under different layouts at 360 days.

590 **5 Conclusions**

591 This study establishes an ETHM multi-field coupling model for CBM recovery.
 592 The model investigates the migration and stimulation mechanisms of methane in
 593 hydraulically fractured CBM reservoirs under microwave irradiation. It also analyzes
 594 the thermal and mass transfer features of the triple pore-fracture structure coal seams
 595 during microwave heating. A series of key parameters were studied to assess their

596 effects on gas production efficiency and reservoir characteristics. The following
597 conclusions were drawn:

598 1) Microwave heating significantly enhances gas desorption and migration. Under
599 microwave irradiation, the area near the waveguide port heats up quickly. As the
600 irradiation time progresses, the high-temperature region gradually extends inward,
601 raising the overall temperature. Under the joint influence of temperature and
602 pressure gradients, adsorbed gas continuously converts into free gas and is
603 extracted.

604 2) Low-frequency microwaves have stronger penetration depth and heating effects
605 than medium and high frequencies. At a frequency of 915 MHz, the coal seam
606 temperature and production increase the most, indicating that microwave
607 irradiation at this frequency is the most effective. To ensure high efficiency in long-
608 term gas extraction, low-frequency microwaves should be selected for assisted gas
609 extraction.

610 3) Higher microwave power results in greater cumulative gas production. Through
611 360 days of extraction, the cumulative production at microwave powers of 0 W
612 and 200 W was 2630 m³ and 3089 m³, respectively, with an increase of 17%.
613 Additionally, higher microwave power leads to higher peak pressures in the matrix
614 along the monitoring line. The gas pressure distribution along the monitoring line
615 from natural fractures presents a funnel shape, with gas pressure decreasing from
616 the waveguide ends toward the production well.

617 4) Increasing hydraulic fracture length significantly improves cumulative gas
618 production. Under conventional extraction conditions, a fracture length of 15 m
619 increases the cumulative output by 17.5% compared to the no-fracture condition.
620 Longer fractures provide more effective gas migration channels, facilitating gas
621 desorption and transport. However, when microwave power is increased to 200 W,
622 the effect of fracture length on production diminishes, possibly caused by the coal
623 matrix expanding thermally, which compresses the fracture structure. The longer
624 the hydraulic fracture, the more significant the pressure drop, which further
625 encourages gas migration. Under high power conditions, the effect of fracture
626 length on gas pressure tends to stabilize, indicating that the fracture structure
627 exhibits higher susceptibility to thermal changes. Therefore, it is crucial to
628 carefully select the combination of hydraulic fracture length and microwave power
629 to enhance CBM extraction efficiency.

630 **Acknowledgments**

631 This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China
632 (12202353, 52274096, 52204112), the Key Research and Development Program of
633 Shaanxi Province, China (2024SF-YBXM-597, 2024SF2-GJHX-49), and the Natural
634 Science Foundation of Shaanxi Province of China (2025JC-YBMS015).

635 **Author Declarations Conflict of Interest**

636 The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

637 **Data Availability**

638 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding
639 author upon reasonable request.
640

641 **References**

- 642 ¹ Z. Tu, L. Li, F. Wang, and Y. Zhang, “Review on separation of coalbed methane by hydrate method,”
643 *Fuel* **358**, 130224 (2024).
- 644 ² Y. Lu, G. Zhao, Z. Ge, Y. Jia, J. Tang, T. Gong, S. Huang, Z. Li, W. Fu, and J. Mi, “Challenges and
645 development direction of deep fragmented soft coalbed methane in China,” *Earth Energy Sci.*, (2024).
- 646 ³ Y. He, X. Li, J. Cai, S. Chen, and X. Li, “Study of Key Factors for Efficient Coalbed Methane Extraction:
647 Pore Structure, Desorption Rate and Seepage Characteristics,” *Langmuir* **41**(9), 6020–6036 (2025).
- 648 ⁴ B. Nie, and S. Sun, “Thermal recovery of coalbed methane: Modeling of heat and mass transfer in
649 wellbores,” *Energy* **263**, 125899 (2023).
- 650 ⁵ H. Wang, L. Wang, S. Zheng, Y. Sun, S. Shen, and X. Zhang, “Research on coal matrix pore structure
651 evolution and adsorption behavior characteristics under different thermal stimulation,” *Energy* **287**,
652 129677 (2024).
- 653 ⁶ W. Tian, W. Yang, L. Luo, G. Si, Z. Zhang, and Z. Zhang, “Water Injection Into Coal Seams for Outburst
654 Prevention: The Coupling Effect of Gas Displacement and Desorption Inhibition,” *ACS OMEGA* **9**(26),
655 28754–28763 (2024).
- 656 ⁷ Z. Li, and Z. Luo, “Environmental impact of hydraulic fracturing on groundwater by isotope
657 composition and hydrochemistry,” *Environ. EARTH Sci.* **83**(20), 580 (2024).
- 658 ⁸ K. Wang, S. Ge, Y. Ma, W. Tan, Y. Hou, Y. Si, A. Ding, and X.-H. Chen, “A thermodynamics-based
659 coupled model for multi-phase flowback in deformable dual-porosity shale gas reservoirs,” *J. Hydrol.*
660 **645**, 132187 (2024).
- 661 ⁹ Z. Hou, Y. Yuan, Y. Chen, J. Feng, H. Wang, and X. Zhang, “A Review of Supercritical CO₂ Fracturing
662 Technology in Shale Gas Reservoirs,” *PROCESSES* **12**(6), 1238 (2024).
- 663 ¹⁰ Y. Lu, H. Li, J. Lu, S. Shi, G.G.X. Wang, Q. Ye, R. Li, and X. Zhu, “Clean up water blocking damage
664 in coalbed methane reservoirs by microwave heating: Laboratory studies,” *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.*
665 **138**, 292–299 (2020).
- 666 ¹¹ R. Liu, X. Dong, and D. Gao, “Investigation on the temperature rise characteristics of radio frequency
667 heating considering water evaporation in low-rank coal,” *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **257**, 124322 (2024).
- 668 ¹² Z. Wang, Q. Guo, X. Cai, J. Zhang, Q. Zhao, B. Li, X. Chen, and H. Gao, “Feasibility Evaluation of
669 RF Heating Heavy Oil Reservoir Based on the Interaction Between Rocks and Electromagnetic Waves,”
670 (2024), p. D032S043R011.
- 671 ¹³ Z.H.Z. Wei, “Mechanisms and technological parameter optimization of near-wellbore laser thermal
672 fracturing for deep coal seams,” *Coal Geol. Explor.*, (2024).
- 673 ¹⁴ A. Gowida, and S. Elkatatny, “Exploring the Potential of Laser Technology in Oil Well Drilling: Recent
674 Advances and Future Recommendations,” (2024), p. D041S051R007.
- 675 ¹⁵ A. Bera, and T. Babadagli, “Status of electromagnetic heating for enhanced heavy oil/bitumen recovery
676 and future prospects: A review,” *Appl. Energy* **151**, 206–226 (2015).
- 677 ¹⁶ F. Huang, C. Liu, S. Cheng, and T. Li, “Microwave thermal regeneration characteristics of spent
678 activated carbon based on a coupled electromagnetic, heat and mass transfer multiphase porous media
679 model,” *Energy* **292**, 130437 (2024).
- 680 ¹⁷ W. Shen, X. Li, T. Ma, J. Cai, X. Lu, and S. Zhou, “High-pressure methane adsorption behavior on
681 deep shales: Experiments and modeling,” *Phys. Fluids* **33**(6), 063103 (2021).

682 ¹⁸ D. Denney, “Cleaning Up Water Blocking in Gas Reservoirs by Microwave Heating,” *J. Pet. Technol.*
683 **59**(04), 76–81 (2007).

684 ¹⁹ J. Fianu, J. Gholinezhad, and M. Hassan, “Thermal simulation of shale gas recovery involving the use
685 of microwave heating,” *J. Pet. Sci. Eng.* **186**, 106768 (2020).

686 ²⁰ H. Li, B. Lin, W. Yang, Y. Hong, and Z. Wang, “A fully coupled electromagnetic-thermal-mechanical
687 model for coalbed methane extraction with microwave heating,” *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* **46**, 830–844 (2017).

688 ²¹ J. Liu, Y. Xue, Y. Fu, K. Yao, and J. Liu, “Numerical investigation on microwave-thermal recovery of
689 shale gas based on a fully coupled electromagnetic, heat transfer, and multiphase flow model,” *Energy*
690 **263**, 126090 (2023).

691 ²² C. Sun, W. Liu, R. Yang, and T. Ma, “Sensitivity analysis on the microwave irradiation enhancing coal
692 seam gas recovery: A coupled electromagnetic-thermo-hydro-mechanical model,” *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.*
693 **100**, 104457 (2022).

694 ²³ J. Huang, G. Xu, Y. Chen, and Z. Chen, “Simulation of microwave’s heating effect on coal seam
695 permeability enhancement,” *Int. J. Min. Sci. Technol.* **29**(5), 785–789 (2019).

696 ²⁴ J. Zhu, H. Wang, Z. Yang, X. Li, and J. Zhou, “Thermal Stimulation on Enhanced Coalbed Methane
697 Recovery Under Microwave Heating Based on a Fully Coupled Numerical Model,” (2022), p.
698 D022S009R001.

699 ²⁵ J. Li, J. Zhang, Q. Xiao, B. Liu, W. Lin, and W. Li, “Experimental Study on Differential Thermal
700 Response and Pore-Fracture Structure Evolution Characteristics of Coals under Microwave Irradiation:
701 A Case Study of Five Different Rank Coals,” *Energy Fuels* **38**(11), 9497–9514 (2024).

702 ²⁶ J. Liu, X. Liang, Y. Xue, S.-T. Li, Y. Fu, X. Liang, and S. Su, “Numerical investigation on the moisture,
703 temperature, and pressure-dependent gas desorption and transport in shale matrix subjected to microwave
704 irradiation,” *Int. Commun. Heat Mass Transf.* **159**, 108146 (2024).

705 ²⁷ Y. Xu, Z. Lun, X. Zhou, G. Zhang, H. Wang, C. Zhao, H. Zhang, and D. Zhang, “Influences of
706 microwave irradiation on pore, fracture and methane adsorption of deep shale,” *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* **101**,
707 104489 (2022).

708 ²⁸ K. Pitchai, J. Chen, S. Birla, R. Gonzalez, D. Jones, and J. Subbiah, “A microwave heat transfer model
709 for a rotating multi-component meal in a domestic oven: Development and validation,” *J. Food Eng.* **128**,
710 60–71 (2014).

711 ²⁹ L. Acevedo, S. Usón, and J. Uche, “Numerical study of cullet glass subjected to microwave heating
712 and SiC susceptor effects. Part I: Combined electric and thermal model,” *Energy Convers. Manag.* **97**,
713 439–457 (2015).

714 ³⁰ J. Liu, J. Wang, C. Leung, and F. Gao, “A Fully Coupled Numerical Model for Microwave Heating
715 Enhanced Shale Gas Recovery,” *Energies* **11**(6), 1608 (2018).

716 ³¹ T. Teng, J.G. Wang, F. Gao, and Y. Ju, “Complex thermal coal-gas interactions in heat injection
717 enhanced CBM recovery,” *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* **34**, 1174–1190 (2016).

718 ³² F. Tong, L. Jing, and R.W. Zimmerman, “A fully coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical model for
719 simulating multiphase flow, deformation and heat transfer in buffer material and rock masses,” *Int. J.*
720 *Rock Mech. Min. Sci.* **47**(2), 205–217 (2010).

721 ³³ H. Zhang, R. Diao, M. Mostofi, and B. Evans, “Molecular simulation of enhanced CH₄ recovery and
722 CO₂ storage by CO₂-N₂ mixture injection in deformable organic micropores,” *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* **84**,
723 103658 (2020).

724 ³⁴ F. Gao, Y. Xue, Y. Gao, Z. Zhang, T. Teng, and X. Liang, “Fully coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical
725 model for extraction of coal seam gas with slotted boreholes,” *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* **31**, 226–235 (2016).
726 ³⁵ T. Xia, F. Zhou, F. Gao, J. Kang, J. Liu, and J. Wang, “Simulation of coal self-heating processes in
727 underground methane-rich coal seams,” *Int. J. Coal Geol.* **141–142**, 1–12 (2015).
728 ³⁶ H. Zhang, J. Liu, and D. Elsworth, “How sorption-induced matrix deformation affects gas flow in coal
729 seams: A new FE model,” *Int. J. Rock Mech. Min. Sci.* **45**(8), 1226–1236 (2008).
730 ³⁷ E. Detournay, and A.H.-D. Cheng, “5 - Fundamentals of Poromechanics,” in *Anal. Des. Methods*, edited
731 by C. Fairhurst, (Pergamon, Oxford, 1993), pp. 113–171.
732 ³⁸ C. Zheng, Z. Chen, M. Kizil, S. Aminossadati, Q. Zou, and P. Gao, “Characterisation of mechanics and
733 flow fields around in-seam methane gas drainage borehole for preventing ventilation air leakage: A case
734 study,” *Int. J. Coal Geol.* **162**, 123–138 (2016).
735 ³⁹ J. Liu, Z. Chen, D. Elsworth, H. Qu, and D. Chen, “Interactions of multiple processes during CBM
736 extraction: A critical review,” *Int. J. Coal Geol.* **87**(3), 175–189 (2011).
737 ⁴⁰ J. Tian, J. Liu, D. Elsworth, Y.-K. Leong, and W. Li, “An effective stress-dependent dual-fractal
738 permeability model for coal considering multiple flow mechanisms,” *Fuel* **334**, 126800 (2023).
739 ⁴¹ Y. Wu, J. Liu, D. Elsworth, X. Miao, and X. Mao, “Development of anisotropic permeability during
740 coalbed methane production,” *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* **2**(4), 197–210 (2010).
741 ⁴² T. Teng, Y. Zhao, F. Gao, J.G. Wang, and W. Wang, “A fully coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical model
742 for heat and gas transfer in thermal stimulation enhanced coal seam gas recovery,” *Int. J. Heat Mass
743 Transf.* **125**, 866–875 (2018).
744 ⁴³ W. Li, J. Liu, J. Zeng, Y.-K. Leong, D. Elsworth, and J. Tian, “A fully coupled multidomain and
745 multiphysics model considering stimulation patterns and thermal effects for evaluation of coalbed
746 methane (CBM) extraction,” *J. Pet. Sci. Eng.* **214**, 110506 (2022).
747 ⁴⁴ W. Li, J. Liu, J. Zeng, Y.-K. Leong, D. Elsworth, J. Tian, and L. Li, “A fully coupled multidomain and
748 multiphysics model for evaluation of shale gas extraction,” *Fuel* **278**, 118214 (2020).
749 ⁴⁵ C.A. Mora, and R.A. Wattenbarger, “Comparison of Computation Methods for CBM Performance,” *J.
750 Can. Pet. Technol.* **48**(04), 42–48 (2009).
751 ⁴⁶ H. Wang, H. Merry, G. Amorer, and B. Kong, “Enhance Hydraulic Fractured Coalbed Methane
752 Recovery by Thermal Stimulation,” (2015), p. D011S004R007.
753 ⁴⁷ H. Wang, O. Ajao, and M.J. Economides, “Conceptual study of thermal stimulation in shale gas
754 formations,” *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* **21**, 874–885 (2014).
755 ⁴⁸ A. Liu, X. Fu, K. Wang, H. An, and G. Wang, “Investigation of coalbed methane potential in low-rank
756 coal reservoirs – Free and soluble gas contents,” *Fuel* **112**, 14–22 (2013).

757